

Kurok Vira Panasivna,

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, Corresponding Member of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine,

*Head of Technological and Vocational Education Department,
Oleksandr Dovzhenko Hlukhiv National Pedagogical University
Hlukhiv, Ukraine,*

Khyman Halyna Petrivna,

*Post-graduate Student of Technological and Vocational Education Department,
Oleksandr Dovzhenko Hlukhiv National Pedagogical University,
Hlukhiv, Ukraine,*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15569463>

DEFINITIONAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPTS “CONDITION” AND “PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS”

Abstract.

The article provides a definitional analysis of the concepts “condition” and “pedagogical condition”. One of the priority areas of the development of the higher education system is to create conditions for the effective training of highly qualified specialists capable of solving complex tasks in professional activity and both professional and personal self-development in the context of European integration processes. Based on the analysis of scientific and pedagogical sources, the article defines the concept “condition” as a complex of circumstances that ensure the possibility of implementing a certain process. The authors determine pedagogical conditions as a certain complex of circumstances that are created and applied by teachers to achieve the pedagogical goal at a higher education institution and to form the future psychologists’ art therapy competence.

Keywords: *condition, pedagogical conditions, educational process, circumstances, art therapy competence, future psychologists.*

The modern Ukrainian national education system is currently undergoing renewal and development due to its integration into the global and European educational space. The key to the successful modernisation of Ukrainian education is the European integration process, which is acquiring new characteristics, e.g. the introduction of effective models and the latest technologies of organising the educational process in higher education. Consequently, it ensures a high level of professional activity and personal qualities for future specialists. As a result, the issue of rethinking and searching for new teaching forms and methods aimed at improving its quality and efficiency, expanding and deepening the content of professional training, is becoming more urgent.

The mentioned factors make it possible to define quality training, driven by the latest trends in the development of social, cultural, and international relations in specialists' professional and pedagogical training, as a priority issue. The following key documents have been implemented to define the directions of Ukraine's educational policy: the Laws of Ukraine “On Education” (2017), “On Higher Education” (2014), the National Qualifications Framework (2011), the Strategy for the Development of Higher Education in Ukraine for 2022-2032 (2022), the New Ukrainian School Concept (2016), the State Standard for Basic and Complete General Education (2011), the Professional Standard for the profession “Psychologist” (2020), the Concept for the Development of Teacher Education (2018), etc.

Implementing the educational process at higher education institutions from the perspective of the new paradigm of the academic sector occurs in the context

of the transformation of values, motives, professional attitudes, and convictions. The future specialist's self-affirmation, self-education, and self-formation while obtaining higher education are grounded on the student's capabilities, abilities, and creative potential [1111].

One of the priority areas of the higher education system development is to create conditions for the effective training of highly qualified specialists capable of solving complex tasks in professional activity and both professional and personal self-development in the context of social, political, economic, informational and psychological instability of modern society.

Implementing pedagogical conditions is a key element in the successful building of future psychologists' art therapy competence. For their identification and theoretical substantiation, it is necessary to analyse scientific approaches to the definition of the concepts “condition” (or “conditions”) and “pedagogical conditions”.

The category “condition” is used in various fields of science to indicate a circumstance that affects some phenomenon or activity. Depending on the relevant context, the word can acquire different semantic connotations. In general, a condition indicates some prerequisite or circumstance that is necessary for the emergence or development of something. As a philosophical concept, “condition” refers to the factors required for the emergence, existence and change of some objects and phenomena [2].

The academic explanatory dictionary of the Ukrainian language provides several meanings of the

term “condition”, including the following: “1) a necessary circumstance that makes it possible to perform, create, form something or facilitates something; 2) circumstances, features of real reality that make something happen or be performed; 3) rules which exist or are established in a particular area of life or activity that ensure the normal operation of something; 4) a set of data, provisions underlying something” [1].

The public electronic dictionary of the Ukrainian language has a similar interpretation of the term “condition”: “circumstances, peculiarities of reality, when something happens or is performed; a set of data, provisions underlying something” [7].

Psychology defines “condition” as a set of external and internal phenomena that are likely to influence the development of a particular mental state. Moreover, the phenomenon is indirectly affected by the activity of an individual or a group of people [10].

Scientific and pedagogical research considers conditions as the characteristics of the educational process ensuring the results of education, training, and personal development (A. Lytvyn) [5]; some circumstances or surroundings that determine the existence of objects or phenomena; a component of the pedagogical system (O. Sahach) [8].

It should be noted that in this context, M. Malkova defines a condition as “the integration of external and internal situations (some activities) of the educational process, the implementation of which depends on the realisation of the intended didactic goal” [6, p. 103].

While generally confirming the above-mentioned interpretations of the concept “condition”, our study considers it as a complex of circumstances that ensure the possibility of implementing a certain process.

Regarding the concept “pedagogical conditions”, the scholars also interpret it from different perspectives. Considering the methodological framework of the concept “pedagogical conditions”, A. Lytvyn defined it as “a complex of intentionally designed main factors of influence on external and internal circumstances of the educational process and personal characteristics of all its participants” [5, p. 32]. Pedagogical conditions provide an opportunity to create a holistic educational environment that meets social needs and the requirements of the labour market. They ensure comprehensive and harmonious development of the individual; provide opportunities for identifying personal potential, considering individual needs, forming universal and professional qualities, and building key general and professional competencies [5].

The Dictionary on Professional Pedagogy defines pedagogical conditions as the circumstances that determine and support the integral pedagogical process of the future specialists' professional training, intermediated by the activity of an individual or a group of people [9].

Pedagogical conditions are considered to be a complex of intentionally defined interrelated and interdependent components of a system, including methods and forms, organisational and motivational activities (individual tasks, youth projects and initiatives, promo-

tions, etc.). It is the integration of objective opportunities for improving the educational process and achieving its goals [3].

The researcher Ye. Khrykov notes that, while factors exist objectively, pedagogical conditions are created intentionally. Thus, he defines pedagogical conditions as “circumstances that determine a direction of development of the pedagogical process”; “a complex of objective possibilities of content, forms, methods, techniques, and means of pedagogical activity”; “objective possibilities of the material and spatial environment” [4].

In our study, pedagogical conditions are defined as a complex of circumstances that are created and applied by teachers to achieve the pedagogical goal at a higher education institution and to form the future psychologists' art therapy competence.

Finally, considering the above-mentioned in the context of the research problem, pedagogical conditions create the educational environment at higher education institutions that ensures the integrity and productivity of the educational process, resulting in the successful building of future psychologists' art therapy competence.

The prospects for further research include the determination of pedagogical conditions for building future psychologists' art therapy competence while professional training at higher education institutions.

References:

1. Akademichnyi tлумachnyi slovnyk ukrainskoi movy [Academic explanatory dictionary of the Ukrainian language]. URL: <http://sum.in.ua/s/kryterij> (Last accessed 08.04.2025).
2. Filosofiia: slovnyk terminiv ta personalii [Philosophy: a dictionary of terms and personalities] / Blikhar V. S., Kozlovets M. A., Horokhova L. V., Fedorenko V. V., Fedorenko V. O. Kyiv : KVIC, 2020. 274 p.
3. Horokhivska T. M. Pedahohichni umovy rozvytku profesiino-pedahohichnoi kompetentnosti vykladachiv tekhnichnykh zakladiv vyshchoi osvity [Pedagogical conditions of development of professional pedagogical competence of teachers of technical institutions of higher education]. *Modern information technologies and innovation methodologies of education in professional Training: methodology, theory, experience, problems*. 2020. Issue 55. P. 221-229.
4. Khrykov Ye. M. Metodolohiia pedahohichnoho doslidzhennia [Methodology of pedagogical research]. 2nd ed. Kharkiv, 2018. 294 p.
5. Lytvyn A. V. Metodolohichni zasady poniattia «pedahohichni umovy» [Methodological principles of the concept “pedagogical conditions”]. 2nd ed. Lviv: LDUBZHD, 2018. 88 p.
6. Malkova M. O. Formuvannia profesiinnoi hotovnosti maibutnykh sotsialnykh pedahohiv do vzaємodii z deviantnymy pidlitkamy [Formation of future social pedagogues' professional readiness for interaction with deviant adolescents]. Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences: 13.00.05 / Taras Shevchenko Luhansk National Pedagogical University. Luhansk, 2006. 255 p.

7. Publichnyi elektronnyi slovnyk ukrainskoi movy [Public electronic dictionary of the Ukrainian language]. URL: <http://ukrlit.org/slovnyk/%D1%83%D0%BC%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B0> (Last accessed 08.04.2025).
8. Sahach O. M. Teoretychnyi analiz poniattia pedahohichni umovy u konteksti profesiinoho zrostan- nia vchyteliv [Theoretical analysis of the concept of pedagogical conditions due to teachers' professional growth]. *Educational horizons*. 2020. № 1 (50). P. 32-35.
9. Slovnyk-dovidnyk z profesiinoi pedahohiky [Dictionary on professional pedagogy] / In A. V. Semenova (Eds). Odesa: Palmyra, 2006. 272 p.
10. Titarenko T. M. Suchasna psykhohohiia osobystosti [Modern psychology of personality]. Kyiv : Marich, 2009. 232 p.
11. Zhdanova V. H. Retrospektyvnyi analiz formuvannia pratseokhoronnykh umin i navychok v peda- hohichnii teorii i praktytsi [Retrospective analysis of labor safety skills in pedagogical theory and practice]. *Bulletin of Chernihiv National Pedagogical University. Pedagogical sciences*. 2013. Issue 108. Vol. 1. P. 193-197.